

White Paper

Participatory Approaches with Older Adults
in Technology and Innovation: Challenges,
Opportunities, Experiences, and Future Directions

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Working Group 3: Technology and Innovation

Participatory Approaches with Older Adults in Technology and Innovation: Challenges, Opportunities, Experiences, and Future Directions

Arlind **Reuter**, PhD (Lund University, Sweden)

Alexander **Kucharski**

(Institute for Work and Technology, Germany)

Seran **Demiral**, PhD (Boğaziçi University, Türkiye)

Eleanor **Bantry White**, DPhil

(University College Cork, Ireland)

Peter **Enste**, PhD

(Institute for Work and Technology, Germany)

Willeke **van Staaldunen**

(AFEdemy, Academy on age-friendly environments, Netherlands)

Ittay **Mannheim**, PhD

(Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Israel)

Krzysztof **Klincewicz**, PhD, DSc

(University of Warsaw, Poland)

Mariana **Buciuceanu-Vrabie**, PhD

(National Institute for Economic Research, Moldova)

Giana Carli **Lorenzini**, PhD (Technical University of Denmark)

Yasemin Demir **Avci** (Akdeniz University, Turkey)

Sonay **Caner-Yildirim**, PhD

(Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University, Türkiye)

Cecilia **Sik-Lanyi**, PhD, DSc

(Hungarian Research Network, Hungary)

Zsuzsu **Tavy**

(The Hague University of Applied Sciences, The Netherlands)

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Executive Summary

Ageing is a critical global issue due to longer lifespans and the evolving needs and abilities of older adults, particularly in the context of technological advancements and digitalisation. The need to include older people in digitisation processes is particularly acute in the European context, where ageing populations have become prevalent in developed and developing countries alike. PAAR-net COST Action (CA22167) aims to:

- Create an age-inclusive environment, enabling citizens to act as agents of their own lives and social surroundings,
- Address the diverse needs, abilities, and expectations shaped by socioeconomic backgrounds, gender, culture, and language through participatory approaches (encouraging older adults to choose to become agents of social change and ensuring that their voices are heard),
- Conceptualize the intersection of technology, innovation, and participatory approaches with older adults. The Working Group 3 (WG3) within PAAR-net focuses on addressing these issues and advancing understanding in this area,
- Highlight current topics in increasingly digitalising societies, focusing on definitions of technologies and innovation and exploring the intersecting experiences of digital and social exclusion that older adults are likely to face, as well as the concept of the silver economy, emphasising its relevance in researching ageing and societal change while recognising the memorandum of understanding of PAAR-net and understanding the necessity of implementing participatory approaches from the design of research or innovation to the project process and outcomes.

In this context, we propose narratives of technology and innovation as solutions to the perceived problem of ageing and the “digital ageism” concept as one of the main challenges for our working group. We then respond to these challenges using a strategic approach to work with the older population on technology and innovation, called “WG3’s techno-innovative approach to older people’s challenges”. The WG3 approach enhances older adults’ social inclusion through participatory approaches. Rather than relying on a solutionist or researcher-centred perspective. We propose using participatory approaches to develop strategies that addresses the challenges older people face as a result of technological advances and rapid digital changes in the world. We focus on a citizen-science approach, including older people as co-creators of scientific knowledge and practical outcomes. The WG3 approach opens discussions on the potential of participatory approaches in technology and innovation across health, care, mobility, energy, community participation and action, environment, food, information and communication technologies, artificial intelligence, and smart technologies fields, emphasising the diversity within older populations through a multidisciplinary and international lens. That also covers the methodological challenges and issues arising from the lack of complete and meaningful participation of older adults in various country settings and the objective to provide a future outlook for more comprehensive and efficient research and practice in these areas.

To share diverse experiences with those approaches, we concentrate on examples where older adults become active co-creators in different country settings (experiences provided by WG3 members from over ten countries). That highlights the importance of participatory approaches, including the products, tools, materials, and processes used in co-creation as distinct aspects of technology and innovation.

We recognise the significance of engaging older adults in new social products and meaningful encounters design and innovation, including non-digital innovations and everyday objects integration into societal environments. Sharing insights and experiences from case studies and multinational research projects allows us to discuss the challenges and opportunities of participatory approaches with older adults in technology and innovation, ultimately pointing out future directions for co-creating our collective future.

1

INTRODUCTION

The ability to meaningfully engage with digital technologies is crucial for staying connected, accessing services and participating in various aspects of life in today's society. Older people tend to interact digitally less often compared to other age groups, potentially leading to intersecting experiences of digital and social exclusion (Seifert et al., 2021).

The causes of the non-use of digital technologies in later life vary. The most common ones include:

- ➔ **psychological factors (attitudes, anxiety, frustration),**
- ➔ **health-related factors (technology accessibility),**
- ➔ **socioeconomic factors (education level, income and geographic location) (Gallistl et al., 2020).**

However, many older adults have started to embrace the internet and digital tools, finding diverse and meaningful ways to integrate them into their daily lives. A growing number of older adults use the internet to stay in touch with family and friends through social media and video calls (Zhao et al., 2022), participate in online learning opportunities (Morrison & McCutcheon, 2019), and access healthcare services (Hall et al., 2015). Some older adults take on roles as digital tutors within their communities, sharing their knowledge and experience with peers who may be less familiar with technology (Korpela et al., 2023) and creating digital content (Brewer & Piper, 2016). That highlights the importance of addressing barriers to digital engagement among older adults and recognising and supporting already active participants in the digital world.

Technology and Innovation Definitions

Technology management scholars have traditionally interpreted technologies as combinations of physical artefacts, human knowledge and knowledge-based processes encompassing social and organisational aspects (Kuehn & Porter, 1981; Bijker, Hughes & Pinch, 1989). They emphasise the gradual emergence of technologies from interactions between users and physical artefacts (Bijker, Hughes & Pinch, 1989), the active role of users in the processes of shaping and using technologies (Orlikowski, 1992) and the technological equivocality with their hybrid and unstable characteristics (Weick, 2000). French philosopher Bernard Stiegler proposed to interpret technology as “inorganic organised beings” (Stiegler, 1998), a material outcome of human knowledge and organisational efforts used for practical purposes. Thus, technology could comprise of:

- products (with end users),
- tools or equipment (supporting the development of products or delivery of services),
- components,
- advanced materials,
- production processes (as inputs contributing towards the development of products).

All these technology forms leverage human knowledge embedded into physical forms that address specific practical problems. Technological areas particularly relevant for participatory approaches with older adults include:

- Health (medical devices and monitoring applications, pharmaceuticals and therapies),
- Care and mobility (assistive technologies, human-robot interaction devices),
- Energy and environment (smart home solutions supporting household heating, cooling and waste management),
- Food (food products, ingredients and nutraceuticals targeting healthy ageing),
- Information and Communication Technologies (hardware and software, including the use of robotics and artificial intelligence),
- Everyday consumer objects and the Internet of Things (age-appropriate product packaging and household devices),
- Constructed environment (suitable ways of urban planning, architecture, interior design, utilities and transportation systems).

Technology does not equate to innovations since not every type has innovative characteristics, and many users intentionally adopt non-innovative, proven technologies. Innovations tend to be interpreted by the methodological standards proposed by OECD and Eurostat (2018) as new or improved products or processes made available to potential users, significantly differing from what has previously been available or used (OECD/Eurostat, 2018: 20). Non-technological innovations include novel social practices (e.g. clinical pathways, approaches to social care, discursive therapies, citizen services or user support). The broad concept of innovation also encompasses social innovations aimed at improving the welfare of individuals and communities (OECD/Eurostat, 2018: 61).

Moreover, the so-called “silver economy” – comprising the economic opportunities associated with an ageing population – drives the inclusion of older adults in the tech market and innovation sector. As the demographic of older adults grows, so does their influence on the market, leading to increased innovation and investment in technologies that cater specifically to older adults. Therefore, the silver economy focuses on products and services consumed independently by older people, covering many areas, including healthcare services, age-friendly technologies, housing, mobility, leisure activities and care. The silver economy term can be viewed within European politics as a counter-narrative to ageing becoming a healthcare challenge and a budgetary burden, but more so in conjunction with innovation. However, its intense focus on technological innovation supporting active and healthy ageing still contributes to ageist narratives, assuming ageing is a problem and positioning older adults as a homogenous consumer group lacking diversity (Lipp & Peine, 2022).

Participatory Approaches with Older Adults

Our PAAR-net working group on technology and innovation seeks to improve knowledge of participatory approaches involving older adults in today's digital world. That comprises understanding the worlds of:

- highly connected older adults,
- individuals struggling with using computers, smartphones, or the Internet,
- those lacking the necessary devices or software to engage effectively.

Drawing on insights from across 28 COST-affiliated countries, we aspire to develop good practices on participatory approaches, applying to older adults in the modern digital landscape.

The concept of participatory approaches as an umbrella term refers to different approaches that aspire to incorporate older adults as co-creators in research and innovation projects, such as community research, participatory action research, collaborative research, or co-research (Urbaniak & Wanka, 2024). Similarly to the pluralism in these approaches, our working group consists of diverse members with wide-ranging expertise and perspectives on participatory approaches. We align on a shared vision of participatory approaches with older adults as active co-creators in technology and innovation projects. We acknowledge the importance of actively recognising and including the expertise of older adults with a wide range of digital skills in technology and innovation settings. We aspire to advance beyond a traditional view of older adults as passive recipients of technology-related innovation and solve the problem of age-related health decline. Recognising and involving older adults as active participants in the technological and innovation sectors allows us to create effective socio-technical ecosystems that resonate with older adults' lived experiences.

This paper seeks to explore key concepts related to participatory approaches with older adults in the field of technology and innovation, including:

- Identifying the challenges and opportunities of participatory approaches with older adults in technology and innovation projects,
- Showcasing current practices of using participatory approaches by presenting several case studies from different countries and various research settings within our working group and discussing commonalities and differences across these cases,
- Deriving initial directions that can inform future participatory approaches with older adults in the field of technology and innovation,
- Exemplifying strategies and methods used in various cultural and economic contexts to prevent digital exclusion among older adults,
- Discussing how to effectively engage older adults in shaping future research, practice, and policy directions, through participatory approaches.

2

CHALLENGES:**COUNTERACTING SOLUTIONIST AND AGEIST TECHNOLOGY NARRATIVES**

The discourse around technology and ageing in policy has long been dominated by what Neven and Peine call a “crisis account of ageing”, and a “triple-win-rhetoric” (Neven & Peine, 2017), with technology perceived as the “solution” to the challenges caused by an ageing population. Societies expect to benefit by significantly reducing the costs of health and social care services through successful technological interventions in aged care. Moreover, societies should profit from economic growth that comes with market-ready and successfully adopted technologies by a growing number of older consumers in the silver economy.

Finally, older persons are coined as beneficiaries of technology, as it allows better quality of care or ageing in place. Examining the discourse from the critical gerontology perspective, Neven and Peine point to the problems affecting developmental research and practice in the ageing and technology fields (2017). As older persons are a heterogeneous group, e. g. in terms of health, lifestyles, economic and social resources, digital competencies, and personal needs for care services, it is difficult to assess whether or not (new) technologies fit the lives of older people. Thus, generalised images of older people and their needs become problematic. Additionally, the ageing and innovation discourse tends to be centred around images of declines in health and functional capabilities with technology can be helpful interventions (Neven & Peine, 2017). This trend is mirrored in research fields such as Human-Computer Interaction, which tend to frame ageing as a problem that can be managed by technology (Vines et al., 2015), and only more recently started to connect discourses of critical gerontology with discourses on technology and innovation.

The reliance on the development of technology based on homogeneous representations of older people brings the risk of materialising stigmatising technologies which older people do not consider relevant to their own lives and, thus, will struggle to use (Peine & Neven, 2017). This concern is explored further by Mannheim & Köttl (2024), who identify the implications of ageism at the macro, meso and micro levels on design, implementation and digital technology application. Distinguishing the levels at which ageism operates enables researchers, policy-makers and other stakeholders to consider how ageism is reflected in technology design and how design can reflect and amplify discrimination and exclusion. Mannheim & Köttl (2024) also draw attention to how negative stereotypes about ageing can shape an older adult's beliefs about their ability to use technologies, in turn, impacting their engagement with technologies. Negative age-related stereotypes shared across a people's network further reinforce exclusion and discrimination that impede technology adoption and engagement. Importantly, positive technology-related interactions, interventions, and participatory approaches in the design process might mitigate the consequences of digital ageism.

3

USING PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES TO RESPOND TO EXISTING CHALLENGES

As suggested by other studies (Gutman & Sixsmith, 2013; Peek et al., 2014; Reeder et al., 2013), incorporating older users into research and design work through a participatory approach would be one way of counteracting these problems and the possible consequences, and harnessing the potential of technology for older users. Engaging older adults in the design, development, and implementation phases is essential for creating inclusive and effective technology solutions. It can help address older adult's specific needs and challenges, such as age-related obstacles, possibly contributing to social isolation and a diminished quality of life. Actively involving older adults in the development process allows these technologies to be better aligned with the older population's preferences and capabilities, leading to higher adoption rates and a more significant positive impact on well-being in later life.

The significance of participatory approaches with older adults in the technology and innovation fields is reinforced by research that underscores the benefits of user involvement. Mannheim et al. (2019) argue that excluding older adults from the design process can result in technologies that fail to fully meet a user's needs due to underlying ageist assumptions. In turn, including older adults is vital for creating technologies and innovations that truly enhance older adults' well-being. Similarly, LaMonica et al. (2021) found that co-design methods help ensure that digital health tools are not only accessible and user-friendly but also effective in improving mental health outcomes for older adults. Fischer et al. (2019) further highlight that involving older users in technology design leads to better learning, improved designs, and a stronger sense of participation, all critical for successful technology adoption.

Current examples of participatory practices for involving older adults in digital technology development are co-design workshops, focus groups, and participatory design sessions. These methods allow technology designers to incorporate older adults' insights and create more user-centred solutions. Research shows that technical knowledge is not enough to produce user-friendly technologies, technology developers also need to understand the end user and the user environment regarding ecological validity, cultural differences, motivating scenes, and differences between the ideas and needs of older users and those of the developer (Sik-Lanyi, 2024). This may include using participatory methods to help developers better understand technological requirements, such as the removal of unnecessary sound effects, using appropriate font sizes and the use of colour to support older individuals with functional limitations (Uysal, 2020; Doğan Merih et al., 2021; Weck, & Afanassieva, 2023). LaMonica et al. (2021) conducted four participatory design workshops with 21 older adults, using activities like group discussions and user journey development. This approach significantly improved the usability and relevance of health technologies, particularly in supporting mental health. Another innovative approach is „unfettered design,” introduced by Fischer and Östlund (2020). This method allows older adults to freely explore and generate design ideas without traditional constraints, uncovering novel insights and addressing issues like power imbalances in the design process. By focusing on participants' views and maintaining flexibility, “unfettered design” effectively leverages the unique experiences of older adults, fostering innovative and aligned technologies.

Participatory approaches may also be used to improve older adults' use of technology. Digital literacy training can be organised for older adults to teach a wide range of technology skills. This training can be supported by a step-by-step curriculum using understandable and simple language (Doğan Merih et al., 2021; Arias López et al., 2023), depending on the existing skill set of the older individual. Family members and caregivers should be included in these training sessions. Social networks and communities supporting older adults in technology use may encourage sharing knowledge and experiences (Uysal, 2020).

The WG3 Methodological Approach: Responsiveness to Challenges

Despite the benefits of participatory approaches in the field of technology and innovation, multiple studies show that the practical realisation of participatory approaches with older persons in the technology and innovation space is facing often intertwining ethical, methodological and practical challenges (Fischer et al., 2020; Merkel & Kucharski, 2018; Mannheim et al., 2023). Most of these challenges mirror the problems with the general ageing and technology discourse. Therefore, they need to be considered when applying participatory approaches. Fischer notes that user involvement may be limited by stereotypes, reducing active participation (Fischer et al., 2020). Mannheim found a gap between the perceived ideal of involving older persons throughout the design process compared to actual involvement in practice (Mannheim et al., 2023). As such, highlights the importance of addressing biases on how older people should be employed, including ageist discourses. Meaningful engagement with relevant and diverse groups of older people, aligning consent processes, and ensuring respect and autonomy for older people in design.

Furthermore, there is an increasing need for research methods that account for sensory decline, privacy, and security concerns. The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated these challenges, particularly in remote settings. Paluch found that digitally mediated participatory projects during the pandemic exacerbated experiences of the digital divide and difficulties in maintaining engagement (Paluch et al., 2023). Similarly, D’haeseleer identified challenges in adapting human-centred design processes for older adults, especially regarding age-related impairments and comfort with new technologies (D’haeseleer et al., 2021). Below, we outline how some of these methodological challenges come to be integrated within the strategy of our working group on participatory approaches with older people in technology and innovation.

Ensuring the Technology and Innovation is Age-Inclusive

As mentioned above, diverse challenges and boundaries that older adults face tend to intersect, leading to potential exclusion from both social life and digital realms. Overcoming such exclusion requires careful consideration of older adults' meaningful participation as active representatives and creators of their own lives and lived citizenship experiences (the importance of participatory methods highlighted in, for instance, Amaro et al., 2020; Slaus et al., 2015). The age-inclusive approach for ageing research across all disciplines, particularly in our working group, focusing on the digital sphere and emerging advanced technology, is crucial to achieving that. Innovation should be considered a strategy and key term for the scope and aims of the WG3 innovative principles and methods are also essential for engaging more older people. That includes those from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds, with varying physical and social capabilities, as well as other relevant societal factors that contribute to diversity among older co-creators.

Considering Heterogeneity Through International and Interdisciplinary Perspectives

Carefully considering the heterogeneity of older persons has fundamental relevance. The question of who should be involved tends to be answered by the study context and „who is immediately affected“. Nonetheless, as older people's lives differ considerably, decisions may entail the risk of excluding relevant people.

Consequently, they may increase or reproduce social inequalities or stereotypes when designing technologies based on simplified images of older people. Therefore, deciding who to include poses a significant challenge, as socially disadvantaged people are usually less likely to participate in research (Aner, 2016). Apart from whom to involve, the question of how to involve older persons and the reasons for their involvement need to be reflected. In the context of PAAR-net, the focus and understanding of our working group connects with various disciplines, such as the development of technologies and innovations and their social and cultural integration in e-health and medicine, care in households or institutions, and digital transformation. Therefore, our research teams intend to develop multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary perspectives by questioning in which fields and research environments (e.g., health and clinical services, civil society and rights-based organisations, households and families, daily care institutions, adult learning centres) researchers and innovators can cooperate with older adults.

Because technological access and digital competencies of people differ across places, regions, and countries, and according to socioeconomic status, educational background, gender, and age groups, an inclusive approach considering all the diversity among older members of society within a transnational and multicultural perspective is necessary. The roadblocks to participation derive from individuals, institutions, and other limitations such as a lack of participatory culture or familiarity with research and relevant practices, discouragement due to old age or other disadvantageous variables, which act as obstacles to social inclusion and diversity in everyday encounters, tangible solutions and impacts of the research are also aimed to be investigated and revisited by sharing experiences. Therefore, partnerships between nations and countries, including physical and virtual realms as common public spaces where we can gather as co-researchers of all ages and backgrounds, are aimed to be achieved.

Developing New Creative Forms of Participatory Engagement

In this context, the specific research design and methods are crucial, as methods usually allow different degrees of participation, and overall designs determine what can be influenced at all (e.g., stage of the research or innovation process). To this end, specific cases from different countries and academic fields are valuable for developing creative, experimental and flexible methods and tactics for working with older adults. Since academic research in the field of ageing mainly focuses on quantitative and qualitative methods, participatory approaches that bring cooperation and reciprocity to research and practice are needed. While participatory approaches in ageing challenge the traditional research power hierarchies, meaningful involvement of older people might be understood differently. Decisions might become problematic because they may be challenged by the interdisciplinary partners' differing understandings of the participatory approach or set in the context of the limited resources or objectives of the project associates. Recent reflections on participatory approaches in intergenerational settings within the technology space show significant variation in the reasons for applying technology-related methods, often influenced by the tendencies and confidence levels of older participants (e.g., Cucinelli et al., 2017; Gomes et al., 2018). In such cases, full participation is not always possible due to the diverse expectations and capabilities of the participants. The studies mentioned above also highlight the challenges that emerge during the participatory process, which play a crucial role in the reevaluation and implementation of full participation in future research.

In the face of the challenges of participatory approaches deriving from their unstructured form, creative research design, including technology and discussions around technological advances and the impacts of innovations on older adults' experiences, can encourage individuals to participate in the preparation, implementation, dissemination, and communication stages. Only through this can an entire participatory process be achieved. AI technology experiences, reflections on future visions and speculative thinking on technology design advancements constitute a few examples of providing participants with creative social engagement. Accordingly, research questions and specific working topics could be uncovered with older adults. However, researchers may be restricted to creative methods in their research environments, depending on the participants' intentions. These challenges can be addressed during the development and implementation stages through workshops and interactive research processes. Furthermore, stages following the research or practice, such as disseminating activities and research findings, should also involve the contributions of older adults, particularly their perceptions and approaches. Participation in decision-making processes is crucial during these later stages as well.

Overall, despite the potential methodological challenges we experience as researchers from different fields, our working group 3 is united by our focus on working with people on-site collaboratively and inclusively. That includes defining the role of older co-creators and exploring tactics and trajectories to engage them as producers and innovators of their own needs and expectations. Meaningful participation should be considered at various stages of the research, technology, and innovation process – from the preparation stage to the final results.

Future Outlook: Experimental Perspective on Participatory Approaches

The involvement of older people in the technology and innovation design process in a participative way from the beginning and throughout the process has been recognised as good practice. It is essential for creating useful and adopted tech and innovations. Nevertheless, while scholars and entrepreneurs generally agree with this notion in practice, we often witness a gap in its pursuit (Fischer et al., 2021; Mannheim et al., 2023). Many ongoing studies seek to establish precisely that through methodological and experimental testing of the intervention aspects and benefits of participatory approaches. Do they lead to innovations perceived as more applicable and acceptable? That could be achieved, for example, by testing the acceptability of prototypes designed with or without older people, or examining how participatory approaches change the perceptions of designers and digital innovation trajectory.

4

PAAR-NET WG3 MEMBERS EXPERIENCE IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES

We now present experiences written by WG members. These accounts represent current understandings and experiences of using participatory approaches with older adults in technology and innovation across more than ten countries, including Türkiye, Poland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Greece, Italy, Germany, Sweden, Hungary and Moldova. The experience case studies were not edited to grasp the diversity of experiences of our WG members. In our commentary, we highlight how our PAAR-net working group can serve as a platform to develop these approaches further and link in with the opportunities outlined in section 3. The experiences address various aspects of ageing studies and participatory practices involving older individuals across digital and physical realms, showcasing the connections with other WGs within the diverse focus areas of our WG. We summarise the topics as follows:

- digital inclusion of older adults and age-friendliness in digital environments,
- providing a bidirectional learning environment between participants,
- developing policies to enhance the engagement of older adults via active ageing,
- innovative co-design experiences in food products,
- ageing in place with welfare technologies,
- and supporting older individuals to age in place by empowering them through participatory solutions.

Even though the following accounts cover unique country experiences, there are intersections in the experiences that cut across country contexts. For instance, Mariana Buciuceanu-Vrabie provides insights from “Active and Healthy Ageing” programs in the Republic of Moldova, and Seran Demiral highlights the ageing population in Türkiye referring to several studies and summarising the conditions of older adults to underline ageing with digital technologies. Age-friendliness is another crucial topic, as accentuated by Yasemin Demir in her discussion of digital applications and platforms provided in Türkiye and by the eco- and age-friendly solutions within participatory approaches in the ongoing AFECO project in different countries. Providing details and discussing expected outcomes of the AFECO project, Willeke van Staalduinen and Zsuzsu Tavy offer insights from The Netherlands, Portugal, Italy, Poland, Greece, and Germany, stressing how e-learning environments support individuals in ageing in place.

A case study from Nordic Countries with a specific focus on Sweden by Giana Carli Lorenzini also opens a discussion on the opportunities presented by digitalisation. These examples demonstrate the connections between place and technology (referring to WG2). In another instance, Krzysztof Klincewicz, based in Poland, explores a study involving 19 European countries on the co-creation of food products with consumers, focusing particularly on the preferences of older adults, which also highlights the need for healthy and smaller unit food options (referring to WG1 and WG2). Finally, Cecilia Sik-Lanyi provides insights from different cases from Hungary, highlighting connections with healthcare and Active Ageing (referring to WG1) in the context of the country growing aged population while underscoring efforts to support university lecturers in ICT usage.

Insights from the Turkish Context in Ageing with Technology

Seran Demiral

(Boğaziçi University, Department of Primary Education, Istanbul, Türkiye)

Türkiye is an ageing country. In 2018, the proportion of older people amounted to 8.8% of the total population. This figure rose to 10.2% in 2023, accounting for 8.5 million people. According to the Turkish Statistical Institute (TurkStat, 2023), in 2018, among those aged 65 and over:

- 62.2% were between 65 and 74,
- 28.6% were between 75 and 84,
- 9.2% were over 85.

By 2023, these percentages had changed to 64%, 28.1%, and 7.9%, respectively. The population pyramid of Türkiye indicates that the percentage of older adults in the country should reach approximately 25% by 2080. As the population ages rapidly, the number of social policies, academic research, and civil society efforts in the ageing area has been increasing. Technology also plays a significant role in this regard.

Recent research studies on the roles of technology and innovation in older adults' lives or their perceptions of ageing are mostly quantitative, with scales used or developed for researching older adults' social aspects. Studies on older adults' technology use and the effects of their technological interaction (e.g., Özsungur 2019; Kalinkara & Sarı 2023; Tamkoç et al. 2023) demonstrate that life satisfaction, independence, active participation in social life, ageing in place, and maintaining social connections reveal a positive correlation with using technology and being open to learning new technologies.

Conversely, the research also highlights the literature on social media use, technology, and innovation usually does not include older people, as older individuals tend not to be active technology users. Suggestions in the existing literature for promoting active and successful ageing include the involvement of social support, acceptance of gerontechnology by older people and intergenerational communication.

Ageing in digital realms and ICT use among older adults become crucial topics in the Turkish context. Statistics on ICT usage in households highlight the change in mobile internet usage among people aged 64-75. The ratio of internet usage in this age group was 0.4% in 2004 and reached 19.8% in 2019. Due to the effects of quarantine during COVID-19, a drastic increase can be seen from 2019 to 2020.

In 2020, 27.1% of older adults used the Internet – 34.9% of males and 20.4% of females. By 2023, the percentages increased to 40.7% for the total population aged 64-75, including 49.8% for males and 32.7% for females (TurkStat, 2023). The digital gap is also a significant topic in researching older adults in Türkiye. It is primarily because it is a developing country with a population of over 85 million, and secondarily due to diverse segments from different regions, including rural-urban differences and gender gaps, related to socioeconomic status and educational levels. Men in Turkey, especially among older generations, tend to be relatively better educated and economically privileged compared to older women. Research focusing on such differences from an intersectionality perspective, identifying socioeconomic status (SES) and gender differences, remains limited. Qualitative research seems on the rise, especially in the sociology of ageing and gerontology regarding technology and innovation.

Turkish Case Study: Digital Inclusiveness Project

Civil society organisations and social workers appear more interested in older people's digital skills. For instance, the "Digital Inclusiveness Project for +65" aimed to provide digital literacy for individuals in this age group. Given the evident need for digital empowerment of older adults following COVID-19, this project was initiated under the coordination of the Elderly Rights Association in Türkiye, in collaboration with 50 Plus Hellas, Greece's most active and experienced organisation in the field of ageing. The project's goals were to improve the digital skills of older adults and to increase public awareness of the digital inclusiveness and social engagement of older people in Türkiye and Greece. As of September 2022, the project reached 800 participants in Türkiye and 160 in Greece and is still ongoing.

This project provides a notable example of supporting older adults' engagement in the digital world by educating them about smartphone use, internet literacy, e-government use, online banking, mobile applications, online shopping, communication, and video conferencing. The reports (65+ Yaşlı Hakları Derneği, 2022) provide information on andragogy (adult education), cognitive capabilities in ageing, as well as technology intelligence and the required technology literacy for older adults. While the target group was those aged 65 and over, the project results are also valuable for those working with older adults on technological literacy.

The technology use of older adults encompasses a variety of options, including mobile health services, medical consultations, ATMs or banking services, and indoor care technologies. In the Turkish context, not only after the pandemic but also following earthquakes and other natural disasters, people have recognized the importance of innovative technologies for individuals with disabilities, as well as those dealing with physical and mental health issues, including older adults (Karasoy & Yıldırım, 2023). Furthermore, social workers and volunteers in organisations have heightened their awareness and interest in the digital literacy of older adults, given the potential challenges posed by natural disasters or other similar difficulties. Furthermore, qualitative studies with an intergenerational focus have become relevant (see Demir Erbil & Hazer, 2021). These studies address not just the possession of devices or use of the internet, but also older adults' purposes for internet use in general, including social media, communication, information access, e-government applications, shopping, and banking services. This topic is also significant in the context of the silver economy. In Türkiye, discussions often focus on the employment of older adults due to economic crises, rather than their roles as consumers in the digital world.

Examples of Age-Friendly Digital Platforms and Applications from Türkiye

Yasemin Demir Avcı

(Department Of Public Health Nursing, Akdeniz University, Antalya, Türkiye)

Turkish population uses e-Nabız as an electronic medical records system. It is an app with health data and personal information collected from various health institutions. The app is available for private citizens and health professionals via the Internet and mobile devices (<https://enabiz.gov.tr/>). The system enables access to outpatient appointments, health histories, prescriptions, health reports, blood tests, radiographs, and allergy and emergency notes for first-, second-, and third-level health institutions. It is user-friendly for individuals aged 65 and over. After making an appointment, this system asks for confirmation from those under 65, while there is no need for confirmation from older adults. For those who cannot use this system, there is the Alo 182 telephone appointment system (<https://www.mhrs.gov.tr/>). If an older person is bedridden, the home care team that they belong to can come to the home to draw blood, remove bedsores, etc. However, patients need to register by calling 4443833.

The system prioritises people aged 65 and over for appointments. In other words, defined daily limits of medical practitioners automatically get assigned to people aged 65 and older (<https://www.mhrs.gov.tr/>).

Final Remarks

Although there are attempts to conduct participatory research with older people, these tend to be limited to user interviews or co-creation during project implementation. The preparation stage and participatory content creation with older adults pose challenges in Türkiye due to a lack of participatory culture and difficulties in accessing older individuals willing to cooperate. Municipalities opening “life centres”, organising workshops for “adults”, or promoting intergenerational encounters play a significant role in fostering cooperation between researchers, older participants, and stakeholders. However, these efforts are still in their early stages.

Furthermore, even the terminology used by organisations or municipalities, such as “mature/adult,” “ageing youth,” or even “plane tree,” refers to the wisdom of older adults but avoids explicitly mentioning their age to encourage participation in organised activities. However, this highlights a crucial issue with language: people often avoid using the word “old” because the inclusive term “older adult” is synonymous with “elder” in Turkish.

Despite these challenges, the recruitment process of older adults into research may face roadblocks due to issues in the collaboration stage between stakeholders, researchers, organisations, community centres, and academia. Overcoming these issues and providing an age-inclusive environment for older adults requires the application of participatory principles. Therefore, terms like “ageing with technology” or “ageing in the digital age” could be a good starting point to engage people, and promote a participatory approach in organisations and civil society that already interact with older adults. Furthermore, participatory approaches should be introduced to social workers in the practical field of design and implementation processes with potential participants.

Digital Integration of Older Adults Through Participatory Approaches in the Republic of Moldova

Mariana Buciuceanu-Vrabie

(National Institute for Economic Research, Republic of Moldova)

The Republic of Moldova faces an accelerated process of demographic ageing. According to recent statistics, the proportion of people aged 60 and over in the population has increased significantly, reaching 23.8% in 2023. That reality requires the development and implementation of effective strategies to support older people in accommodating new technologies and using them to improve their life quality.

In the last two years, efforts to digitally integrate older adults in the Republic of Moldova have intensified significantly, thanks to new initiatives and the expansion of existing programs. The Government of the Republic of Moldova significantly emphasised the importance of the promotion of the digital inclusion of older adults through the Active and Healthy Ageing Program for 2023-2027. The program aims to include developing older people's digital skills and improving their inclusion and social participation levels. This initiative demonstrates the government's firm commitment to digital equity for older people and recognises the importance of a cross-sectoral approach to address the specific needs of this population segment.

At the local level, some initiatives seek to support the digital inclusion of older citizens. One successful case of a participatory approach is the opening of the first Senior Club in Ungheni City, where older people actively engage in learning and using technology.

The Generations United Against Loneliness hackathon was a pivotal event in promoting intergenerational collaboration to develop IT solutions tailored to older individuals' needs. This occasion, which brought together young developers and older adults, underscored the importance of intergenerational collaboration in overcoming digital barriers, inspiring a renewed commitment to the cause of digital inclusion for older people.

Another core aspect of digital inclusion is access to e-health and education services for older people. Starting in 2023, many older people in the Republic of Moldova now benefit from e-health services and online counselling, enabling them to manage their health more autonomously and connect with healthcare providers digitally.

In 2024, at the State University of Moldova, the first students aged 55 and over received their diplomas in an educational program (2023/2024) dedicated to this population segment. This program provides access to continuing education and contributes to digital literacy development, which is essential for their integration into modern society.

Challenges

The digital inclusion of older people in the Republic of Moldova encounters significant challenges, including limited access to digital infrastructure, especially in rural areas, and low levels of digital literacy. According to recent assessments, only one-third of the senior population use the Internet, and their digital skills remain limited, highlighting the urgent need for educational and support interventions.

Older Adult's Participation in Co-Creation of Innovative Food and Packaging

Krzysztof Klincewicz

(Centre for Socially Responsible Innovations, Faculty of Management, University of Warsaw, Poland)

Since 2019, the Centre of Socially Responsible Innovations at the University of Warsaw has coordinated the project called EIT Food RIS Consumer Engagement Labs, and funded by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology based on the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe framework programmes. The Consumer Engagement Labs constitute pre-competitive co-creation sessions involving consumers and producers, meeting in a format of living labs to jointly design new product concepts based on an innovative methodology developed by the University of Warsaw (for further details, see: Klincewicz et al., 2022; Klincewicz et al., 2023; Klincewicz et al., 2024). In 2019-2024, the co-creation processes involved 128 consumer panels, 31 scientific organisations and 61 companies from 19 European countries working together to design, develop and introduce 32 innovative food products. Twenty two of these products were specifically designed by and for older consumers (aged 65+).

Consumer Engagement Labs represent the biggest European food co-creation initiative, serving as an example of participatory approaches with older adults leveraging co-creation and co-design. The participation unleashed the creative potential of older adults, empowering them to propose new products and stimulating the design of technological innovations in food and packaging fields.

Twenty two of these products were specifically designed by and for older consumers (aged 65+). Consumer Engagement Labs represent the biggest European food co-creation initiative, serving as an example of participatory approaches with older adults leveraging co-creation and co-design. The participation unleashed the creative potential of older adults, empowering them to propose new products and stimulating the design of technological innovations in food and packaging fields.

Older consumers designed products considering their specific food preferences, including elimination, reduction or substitution of ingredients that were considered potentially harmful (such as fat, salt, sugar and allergens), use of functional ingredients and increased nutritional value with enhanced protein and micronutrients. They tapped into traditional knowledge, locally sourced ingredients and traditional recipes to inspire food producers through this intergenerational exchange of product proposals, reviving forgotten flavours of their childhood and designing “legacy” dishes in novel, healthier and more sustainable ways. They also looked at ways of making the food more attractive for older consumers through flavours enhancement and utilisation of vibrant colours or atypical shapes and forms. Participation paved the way for offering gourmet products at affordable prices, e.g., consumers worked with Agronomia Agro Food Innovation SRL in Romania to design a product consisting of an exquisite ham, usually beyond their financial reach, but separated into small chunks of meat, easier to chew and digest, combined with an attractively flavoured jelly – thus, finding creative ways of making the high-quality, desirable ingredients available to less wealthy older consumers.

One particularly interesting contribution provided by fellow older adults focused on eating comfort. Consumers tend to enjoy the product's crispiness and crunchiness. Yet, such sensory experiences come with increased risks at the older age due to the weakened teeth, enamel decay and dental prostheses. Foods typically prepared for the older population feature soft textures, easy to chew and swallow, but may seem relatively plain and bland to consumers when eaten regularly. Older people's participation in the new product design process inspired food technologists to seek innovative ways to respond to expressed desires for crunchy textures, non-sticky mouthfeel and oral comfort.

Grikola – a product co-created by Lithuanian consumers and Ekofrisa UAB, offering the sensory experience of eating granola, but made with an ingredient much healthier than roasted oats: organic buckwheat, specially processed to make the buckwheat pieces both crunchy and soft – was one of the results. Similarly, Portuguese consumers, a food producer Vieira de Castro S.A. and a supermarket chain Continente co-created “Bolachas Equilíbrio” – biscuits low in fat, sugar and salt, with healthy whole-grain ingredients processed to make them less sticky to teeth or dentures. The older consumers participation in product co-creation caused companies and food technologists more sensitive to the importance of oral comfort in older age – a problem that had been overlooked or solved merely by offering semi-liquid, soft products, not fully satisfactory for many older consumers.

Another strand of creative contributions by co-creative older adults concerned the convenience of consumption: sensitising food producers to the specific eating circumstances in older age. One-person households prefer smaller unit sizes (to prevent food from going off when not fully used) and combinations of many diverse food options (instead of large, family-size packaging). Older consumers desire healthy snacks eaten in small portions throughout the day or offered to unexpected guests such as grandchildren. Participants also expressed preferences for partially prepared products with opportunity to experience the joy of adapting and preparing the final meal at home, to eat „homemade” dishes, but without the complexity of the fully-fledged cooking.

The creative processes involving older consumers and food companies resulted in multiple innovative products. Some for other consumer groups - e.g., older adults observed the eating habits of their grandchildren, proposing healthy and convenient snacks for the young generation. The Selected Labs processes focused on food packaging. These contributed to redesign of takeaway food packaging based on older adults experiences from the COVID-19 times when used food packaging amassed at homes, with garbage increasingly difficult to dispose. The co-created packaging was easier to open, better separating multiple dishes (e.g., soup, solid food, salad, dessert), preventing spillage and preserving temperatures, and easy to dismantle, take out or partially reuse. **[For more information refer to the [EIT Food RIS Consumer Engagement Labs.]**

Nordic Countries Experiences: Empowering Ageing in Place – Rethinking Welfare Technology and Homecare through Participatory Design

Giana Carli Lorenzini

(Assistant Professor, Dept of Engineering Technology, Technical University of Denmark)

The interest in supporting older people to age in place, i.e., to live in their own homes for as long as possible, continues to grow. It is particularly apparent in Nordic countries, like Sweden, where ageing in place tends to be prioritised through the homecare services provision to support older people in their residency. Yet, augmented demand for home care services combined with scarcity of homecare personnel poses new challenges, as it also offers opportunities for digitalisation, and the provision of welfare technologies (Kim et al., 2017).

In recent years, I have engaged in research projects that explore how older people experience self-care, medication management and daily life. One of those, called “Patient-Centred Pharmaceutical Packaging Design for Enhanced Life Quality of Older People” financed by the Swedish Family Kamprad Foundation, fifteen older adults in Sweden documented their day-by-day of taking multiple medications in diaries (composed of text and pictures taken by them).

Our team pointed out how the design of medication packaging affects uptake. The packaging design of medicines often prioritises the protection of the medicine during transport and distribution, failing to meet older people's needs and sometimes creating packaging almost impossible to open and reuse. While real-life stories came up, it became clear that older people now have more responsibility for their care, but they are not as often involved in deciding how care should be organised at home.

As a consequence, many older adults create their routines combined with coping strategies to deal with overwhelming tasks, like handling complex medication treatment after a stroke. So far, it seems that little is known from the ones producing the medications and their packaging about what happens when medication is placed amid daily living, where other activities take place. Many older adults are quite active and find themselves bound by medication regimes demanding bringing their pharmaceutical product and remembering different dosage intakes during the day. Interestingly, many older people reported that they learned to be their “new self” when chronic age-related illnesses required them to take several medications a day. They indicated sadness and disappointment, as well as empathy for others living in similar conditions (Lorenzini et al. 2022).

In another collaborative project, financed by FORTE in Sweden, researchers from Jönköping University, Lund University, and the Technical University of Denmark collaborated to investigate the experiences of older people and homecare staff with welfare technologies (WTs). WT is digital technologies designed to enable individuals to live securely, actively and independently at home. They are often provided by a local authority, to optimise care, including resource shortage (Socialstyrelsen, 2019; Frennert, 2020). Sweden is quite ambitious, aiming to become a global leader in enhancing population welfare through digitalization, with welfare technology (WT) playing a crucial role (E-hälsa myndigheten, 2022). Examples of WT include:

- night cameras,
- digital locks,
- digital applications for monitoring homecare services performance,
- digital safety alarms to detect falls of older people at home (the most popular one).

The Welfare@Home project's starting point lies in considering that older people and home care workers tend to be the most affected by the WT implementation. However, research describing their experiences with WT is scarce. Moreover, there is a lack of participatory approaches leading to the participation of those groups in technology development and implementation. During the first study in the project, older people (n=26) and homecare staff (n=26) from five different Swedish municipalities were interviewed. Preliminary results show that older adults often lack instruments in their choice of welfare technology and many challenges imposed by the usability of those technologies. On the other hand, home care workers encountered the issue of the WT, not always fitting the needs in terms of schedule and task performance. In this sense, there was also a lack of information about how they plan and perform their work duties when using the WT.

The next step in the project is now to co-create ideas for better implementation and use of welfare technologies in homecare services. It will focus on identifying crucial points for improvements of WT and WT-related ideas for unmet needs as well as the draft guidelines development for implementation, and usage of WT in homecare services that meet the needs and desires of older adults and homecare staff. As a design and innovation scientist, it strikes me that treatment regimens (including medication packaging) and WT schemes continue to be developed without involving older people in the context of their use. As welfare technologies and treatment move to homes, more knowledge and participatory research are needed, as often these technologies are developed with a lack of a human-centred approach – where greater attention is put on the creation of new devices, robots, and gadgets whilst a deep understanding of context, usability and real needs of older people is commonly overlooked.

[More information can be found <https://academic.oup.com/ageing/article/51/3/afac050/6544238?searchresult=1>]

Empowering Older Adults to Apply Affordable Eco- and Age-Friendly Solutions to Age in Place – Participatory Approaches with Older Adults in the Netherlands, Portugal, Italy, Poland, Greece and Germany

**AFECO project Erasmus+ Adult Education
2022-1-NL01-KA220-ADU-000086242, 2022-2025**

Willeke van Staalduinen

(AFEdemy)

Zsuzsu Tavy

(The Hague University of Applied Sciences)

Due to demographic ageing, the older population triggers a series of changes at cultural, institutional, and community levels. European policies show special attention to the empowerment and participation of older people in all aspects of social and economic life and the promotion of positive ageing characteristics, as it is active ageing and ageing-in-place strategies (Kazak et al., 2017). Many older people prefer living at home for as long as possible despite their increasing frailty and complex needs - and that is the core idea of „ageing in place”. Ageing in place now encompasses a broader definition to incorporate features beyond the home, such as the local environment and community (Phillips & Walford, 2011). It is beneficial for older adults to stay in familiar neighbourhoods and communities, maintaining their routines and social connections with a sense of security and belonging.

The AFECO project aims to:

- Develop a well-structured open e-learning platform aiming to raise awareness,
- Educate older people, (in)formal caregivers and social workers regarding the application of age- and eco-friendly principles (in-home and in-neighbourhood settings) aspiring for participants/recipients to age in better physical and mental health, actively participate in society and stay independent and in better health for as much as possible.

Co-design and participatory involvement of older adults are crucial to achieve that. The consortium partners performed structured interviews with open questions with 120 older people (65+) from multiple backgrounds from six countries. The questions regarded the content of learning on age- and eco-friendly principles and the personal methods of learning (personal, group, online, face-to-face, auditive, visual, etc.) Conclusions drawn from the interviews in Greece, Germany, Portugal, Italy, the Netherlands and Poland highlight common themes and unique considerations in developing training offers for older people. There is a general preference for clear and simple training structures, emphasising the importance of catering for different levels of knowledge. The role of technology varies, with some expressing comfort with e-learning environments and others leaning towards face-to-face interaction. To sum up, a successful training offer for older people should be adaptable, combining clear and simple structures with various teaching methods. It should address information gaps, consider the affordability of age- and eco-friendly solutions, and prioritise the social aspect of learning. The different preferences and needs expressed in these countries underline the need for a nuanced and culturally sensitive approach to the development of training offers for older people.

After defining the learning goals and identifying the topics of the modules, another 120 older adults with multiple backgrounds were invited to co-create the learning modules in two rounds. The first round taught the consortium the usage of short paragraphs and modules. To have links to videos and other resources is well-received, but a balance of appropriateness and volume is needed. A common issue in each country is the language barrier. Many older people like to read and hear in their languages instead of the English language. The involved older adults also indicated that they prefer to find their paths within the learning offers and to have practical solutions to apply age- and eco-friendly principles at home or in the community. A second round of co-creation will follow in the Autumn of 2024.

The final participation of older adults in AFECO will be in the e-learning platform testing and validation. Another large group of older adults will be invited to test the e-learning platform fully and give feedback and suggestions for adaptations. The final results are expected in the middle of 2025.

Hungarian Experiences – Digital Integration of Older Adults and Age-Friendly Emergency Call Helping Solution in Hungary

Cecilia Sik-Lanyi

(Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN) Cognitive Mapping of Decision Support Systems research group, Budapest and Department of Electrical Engineering and Information Systems, University of Pannonia, Veszprem, Hungary)

The ageing of the Hungarian and European population, that is, the increase in the proportion of older adults and the simultaneous decrease in the proportion of the young represents a long-term process. As the demographic composition of society changes, we may observe differences in the life conditions of social groups at different ages, and developments in some processes, and phenomena (e.g. career entry, retirement) associated with specific age groups - [on this page](#), you can find content by age group and about special age groups from various statistical domains.

By February 2024, 20% of the Hungarian population is over 65.

The National Strategy concerning the older adults adopted in 2009, (Decision No 81/2009 (X.6.) of the Parliament) was drafted in line with the principles of active ageing. It is stated in the document itself, discussing, in particular, a basic WHO paper published in 2001 that defines policy concerning older adults, called “Active Ageing – Policy Framework”. The latter meant a real breakthrough because it was the first to reflect on older adults as complete human beings, to consider their fulfilment in life, and not reduce them to their social and health-care aspects.

The Hungarian Programme for the European Year of Active Ageing document describes more initiatives for older adults. The work continues, to mention, for example, the development of digital skills for older people.

Old and young age groups constitute equal priority target groups of the activities of public education institutions. Older adults may enjoy many learning opportunities. Popular initiatives include:

- ➔ Mastery of digital literacy skills with a central role,
- ➔ *eMagyarország* (eHungary) points in the majority of libraries,
- ➔ *Kattints rá, Nagy!* (Click on it, Granny!).

Programmes took place continuously throughout the year at community centres – at 20 locations in the country. Although public education statistics somewhat blur the diverse and colourful activities and communities of old age groups, the trends in increasing activity still show in the number of participants of artistic groups and pensioners' clubs and courses. Pensioners' clubs had over 257 thousand members in 2009. Approximately 27 thousand members of artistic groups are 60 years old or older, while this number was close to 16 thousand for training courses. Statistics also show that public education serves older adults well: there are pensioners' clubs 10 operating in half of the smaller municipalities (49%), but groups for the preservation of traditions and amateur folk art groups (47%), which primarily gather older adults, are also present in similar proportions.

A flagship tool for involving older adults in the information society is the *eMagyarország* (eHungary) Programme, which aims to extend internet access to the entire territory of Hungary, mainly focusing on areas less well-serviced or not at all serviced (less-favoured municipalities). For those who do not have broadband internet access in their homes for technical, motivational or financial reasons, it may provide broadband internet access through the construction and maintenance of such points. The goal was, for instance, the use of e-public services or assistance from technicians working there, that is e-Consultants, to become as widespread as possible.

The Hungarian government is determined to support the digital competencies of Hungarian citizens to improve the standard of living of the population. One of the programs of this endeavour was the „Digitalisation for the Active Older Adults” program in 2019.

See here: 1761/2017 adopted by the government. (XI. 7.)

The programme’s purpose was info-communication for older adults over 65 who can leave their homes, providing skills training for the tools used. The programme was open to active older people who, due to a lack of information communication skills, had not been able to use their own digital devices (smartphone, tablet, personal computer) properly up to that point and those who did not have such tools but wanted to learn about them.

As a result of the program, the older adult participants could use their own ICT devices, independently search for information on the Internet, send and receive e-mail messages, active social media portals use and make video calls.

The programme basis was small-group (5-25 people) sessions in which older adults work together so they can master the use of ICT tools. The nature of the sessions is not traditional classroom education but competence development through direct, practical examples. During the sessions, the lecturer-participant knowledge transfer doctrine was supplemented with the knowledge transfer using an interactive method, where the participants' communication with each other and helping each other plays a major role in the learning material in its acquisition and practice. Besides mastering the course material, it was also influential to meet the expectation that the participants had fun during these sessions. A series of sessions with a good atmosphere, in addition to that, provided a pleasant pastime for the older generation, institutions such as to get to know the work taking place in institutions, which he did not have the opportunity to do before.

Moreover, several Hungarian universities have organised Senior University Lectures with pensioners' clubs. During these, university lecturers, well-known artists, and experts deliver university lectures to pensioners.

The experiences are listed below in links showcasing that the events are popular among older adults:

- <https://semmelweis.hu/szeniorakademia/kuldetesunk/>
- <https://uni-pannon.hu/hirek/news-egyetemi-elet/a-tanulas-kortalan>
- <https://uni-milton.hu/szenior-akademia/>
- <https://nyugegy.hu/5-6%20Szenior%20Akad%C3%A9mia.htm>
- <https://www.agoraszeged.hu/hirek/idosek-iskolaja.html>
- <https://unideb.hu/szenior-egyetem>
- <https://nye.sze.hu/nyugdjas-egyetem-gyorben>

The **Gondosóra** programme launched by the Government of Hungary, is a signalling device service available by right of subject free of charge by persons over 65 with Hungarian citizenship and a registered domestic address.

The Gondosóra programme, which is unique in Europe, includes a 0-24-hour dispatch service, where qualified dispatchers provide assistance in solving the problems that arise, if necessary, involving the contact persons (contact family member, neighbour, friend, or optionally a social worker, etc.). Assistance is not only available in the event of an emergency but also means quick support for everyday problems. An era change in safety and a milestone in older adults' care: a great help to users, but also security and peace of mind for the users' family and relatives, knowing that help is available at the touch of a button.

Signing up for and using the Gondosóra programme is free and available in every settlement in Hungary, every day and every hour of the week.

The number of users of the Gondosóra programme, and the number of lives saved with its help constantly increases. So far, the unique initiative has saved the lives of 16,000 older adults. [Here](#), you can find a few extreme examples of how the Gondosóra saved users' lives, e.g., an old fisherman who fell into the water, rescued a lost lady in case of stroke, etc.

By the end of June 2024, more than 650,000 people have already registered for the Gondosóra program. Today, every third of Hungarians over the age of 65 is a user.

All these varied experiences, focusing on the potentials in ageing studies and the challenges and opportunities associated with participatory approaches with older adults, showcase the diverse dynamics in the countries represented by the members of this WG. On one hand, the pitfalls of limited access to digital technologies - particularly about the socioeconomic status of older adults and the urban-rural divide - as well as the challenges to ageing in place due to a lack of digital competency or social exclusion, were emphasised in the Republic of Moldova and Türkiye. Hungary also plays a critical role in this context, as there is a need to improve the digital skills of older adults through educational programs. On the other hand, Sweden, with one of the highest proportions of older adults, demonstrates the necessity of focusing on digital prospects.

Qualitative research examples from Türkiye also highlight the lack of participatory approaches in some cases, emphasising that research involving older adults is still in its early stages due to the growing interest in ageing populations. Knowledge exchange between countries with experience in managing ageing populations and those with emerging ageing populations is crucial at this point. The digital gap among such countries and the associated socioeconomic challenges should be considered to develop inclusive practices across Europe, including both EU and non-EU member countries (with a closer look at the role of ITC - Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Greece, Portugal, Türkiye, mentioned in this paper - as defined by COST).

While most case studies strongly emphasise digital technology, including welfare technologies and innovations in food products, the members contributions in different fields provide a rich perspective. Moreover, the creative outcomes, such as those involving Lithuanian and Portuguese consumers in the Polish case study or the AFECO project, including examples from six different countries, highlight the diversity in the multicultural and multinational backgrounds of the researchers. This diversity also brings challenges in multilingual settings.

Therefore, local languages and place-based experiences play a crucial role in the provided examples, further proving the significance and necessity of participatory approaches.

5

CONCLUSION

Older people's engagement with technology and innovation presents significant opportunities in today's rapidly evolving digital world. Despite traditional views often portraying older adults as passive recipients or non-users of digital technologies, there is a growing recognition of their active participation and valuable contributions. The intersection of ageing, technology, and innovation is about over-coming barriers to digital inclusion and leveraging diverse experiences and expertise of older adults as co-creators.

Participatory approaches - such as co-design workshops, focus groups, and inclusive and creative research practices - emerged as effective methods to involve older adults in technology and innovation projects. These help to ensure technologies are accessible, user-friendly, relevant and beneficial to the end users. However, the participatory approaches implementation comes with challenges such as:

- overcoming ageist stereotypes,
- addressing diverse digital competencies,
- ensuring meaningful engagement across different socio-economic and cultural contexts.

As highlighted by the work of our PAAR-net Working Group 3, a commitment to inclusivity, interdisciplinarity, and creativity is essential to navigate these challenges and to promote a more nuanced understanding of older adults as active agents in their own right.

In the future, the need for further experimental research to empirically establish the benefits of participatory approaches and refine these methods to be more inclusive and effective remains. Continuing to challenge narratives and embrace the diversity within the ageing population allows us to create socio-technical ecosystems that not only cater to the needs of older adults but also empower them as innovators and contributors in the digital age. Our efforts must be focused on fostering an inclusive digital society where older adults are seen not just as consumers of technology but as active participants shaping the future of technologies and innovations.

Research and practical experiences from WG members across the Republic of Moldova, Hungary, Türkiye, Sweden, Poland, Netherlands, Greece, Germany, Portugal, and Italy illustrate the diverse approaches to methodology and knowledge concerning older adults. These experiences reveal differences depending on whether ageing populations become an important issue or are already prioritised by policymakers and researchers. Therefore, it is crucial to interact and exchange knowledge among WG members as participants in the PAAR network.

For future research and policymaking strategies, several questions have emerged from the paper and WG3 discussions:

- How are older adults represented in digital and social media, including the terminology used in local languages? How can we rebuild discourse to counter ageist practices?
- How can we focus on cultural differences and utilise them for creative solutions to foster collaboration as co-creators in our evolving society amidst advancing economic, technological, and political environments?
- How can we promote participatory activities that are easily implemented and engaging for people of different ages (with an intergenerational focus) and demographics (with a multicultural and intersectional focus) to encourage widespread participatory approaches?
- What are the ways to foster solidarity among older adults, particularly those facing more significant difficulties due to intersecting inequalities and injustices arising from gender, ethnicity, or other dimensions that may cause exclusion, in addition to being older citizens in society?
- What are the possibilities and challenges arising from artificial intelligence, software and devices designed for older people to enhance their ageing experiences by evolving and encouraging them to become co-creators of such technology and innovations?
- How can we influence decision-makers to implement strategies that support the well-being of modern older adults and also incorporate these issues into all levels of education to raise awareness among the next generation? What are the ways to facilitate knowledge transfer between researchers from different countries and exchange experiences to develop new strategies on an international scale in this regard?

As noticed in the questions listed above, WG3 approach concentrates on lived experiences in digital realms by incorporating difference-centred approaches; ageing with advanced technologies and engaging with them to enhance ageing practices; accepting and fostering participatory approaches as the key tactics to develop cooperative solutions for both current and future generations as older adults, while also influencing stakeholders for the future. For future trajectories, we should develop strategies to ensure the full participation of contributors in research, practice, production, and policymaking.

Based on our previous work and the discussions that have emerged throughout our collaborations, we have also developed topics related to these questions, including but not limited to:

- framework on PAAR for technology and innovation research, highlighted in this paper,
- digital citizenship of OA and PAAR-net,
- accessibility of the digital world, sought to address here,
- use of generative AI to increase OA's digital competence,
- intergenerational communication through digitally conducted encounters,
- more creative methods to ensure full participation.

Therefore, WG3 aims to highlight specific perspectives on various methods in the forthcoming progress of PAAR-net and to delve into these topics with engaged members in the following stages.

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